

LEGAL LANDSCAPES OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE MALDIVES: EVOLUTION, IMPLEMENTATION, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to document the legal transition of a developing island nation, namely Maldives, to establish a nation-wide inclusive education system that caters to all students, including those with special needs. The study sheds light on the significant milestones achieved, current status of implementation of the legislations, and suggests a roadmap towards achieving inclusion in schools. The investigation draws heavily on the relevant legal, policy, and other local documents to elicit the story on the legal domain. Data from reports and similar documents are used for examining the status of implementation. Major milestones and transitions that took place over the three and half decades in the inclusive education journey of the country are discussed in the paper. These milestones in implementation are cross-checked against the expectations stipulated in the relevant legislations. The study offers recommendations to improve and widen the scope of inclusive education in the country which could be lessons for countries similar in context.

Keywords: challenges, implementation, inclusive education, legal landscape, milestones, recommendations, teacher development.

INTRODUCTION

Amidst the ever-evolving educational landscape, a transformative trend is sweeping across countries, promising a future in which every learner's potential, regardless of the unique abilities and backgrounds, can flourish. Countries endorse and implement both national and international treaties aiming to create inclusive educational environments that recognise learner needs, promote collaboration, and foster positive educational outcomes of individual students (Adams et al., 2021; Štemberger & Kiswarday, 2017; UNESCO, 2004). Similar to many other developing countries, Maldives has undergone substantial revolutions over the years taking significant strides to develop and implement inclusive education practices through formulation and implementation of laws, regulations, and the establishment of inclusive educational institutions within the directives of Ministry of Education.

The journey of inclusive education (IE) in Maldives gained momentum with the ratification of international conventions and frameworks such as United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD), and the Education for All (EFA) framework, which emphasised the importance of IE for children with disabilities and other marginalised groups (United Nations, 2006). Building upon the foundation of these conventions, the Maldivian government implemented other significant policy changes, and legislative measures that shaped the trajectory of inclusive education in the country. Some of these initiatives include, the Inclusive Education Policy (2013), Education Act 2021, and the new Inclusive Education Policy 2021, which set the legal framework for inclusion in educational settings (Moosa et al., 2020; Naseer, 2013; UNICEF, 2011; UNICEF, 2021). Additionally, the Maldives education sector plan (ESP) 2019-2023 accentuated inclusive education as a priority (Ministry of education & Ministry of higher education – MoE & MoHE, 2019). All these initiatives have potential to directly affect IE in the country, as they establish the legal and governance framework by ensuring that educational institutions are held accountable for providing IE to all students.

Despite the significant advancement in the implementation of IE in Maldives, a crucial research gap is identified in literature that mandates further investigation on the topic. First and foremost, there is a need for extensive explorations that examine the effectiveness of inclusive practices, teachers' pedagogical approaches, and support mechanisms that are in place to make IE successful. Likewise, identifying the impact of teacher training, and availability and accessibility of resources that promote implementation of the IE frameworks, is lacking in the existing literature. Additionally, there is limited research that evaluates different countries' legal landscape of IE showcasing diverse paths countries have adopted along their journey of inclusive education. We believe that investigating the legal frameworks is imperative as it would provide a comprehensive understanding of the rights, responsibilities, and obligations of stakeholders that are related to inclusion within the education systems. Delving into the frameworks would enable stakeholders gain insights by identifying inconsistencies and areas of improvement. Such a study would lead to potential future directions that would enhance inclusivity and effectiveness of the country's education in general.

Aligned with the above need, the aim of this case study is to describe the developments and expansion on the legal framework of inclusive education in the Maldives. The study also intends to demonstrate the current state of inclusive education implementation in relation to the expectations of the legal framework, and recommend a way forward for future directions.

BACKGROUND LITERATURE

The global movement for IE is being driven by a number of factors. The growing understanding of the importance of IE as a human rights issue is one of the major driving forces (Mhlongo, 2015). Recognising the importance of IE in fostering social and economic growth is another motivating factor (Afolabi, 2014; UNESCO, 1994). In addition to recognising the advantages of diversity and the need to build a more equitable society, IE works to promote the participation and inclusion of all students in society, and helps to remove barriers and stereotypes that contribute to social exclusion and discrimination. Furthermore, IE is advantageous for not only students with disabilities but also for all students when diversity is embraced through interactions and communication. As such, it is a right for all, whether or not they have disabilities, to be educated in environments that foster inclusivity, collaboration, and interaction. This type of education creates optimal conditions for the academic and personal growth of all students (Billingsley et al., 2018; Hornby, 2015; Muega, 2016).

The educational landscape for children with disabilities in the Maldives significantly evolved over the years. One of the significant policy advancements in the Maldives related to IE was the government's commitment to uphold the rights of persons with disabilities by becoming a signatory to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2007, and subsequently ratifying the Convention in 2010. This ratification imposed obligations on the government to institutionalise measures that guaranteed an equitable educational experience for children with disabilities, similar to their peers without disabilities (UNICEF, 2021c). Since then, numerous developments have taken place, much of which is focused on ensuring inclusive education within the formal education system.

As Maldives education system experienced extensive policy reform activities during the past two decades, its neighboring countries also progressed towards inclusive education. These countries adopted legislative frameworks like the UNCPRD, amending national constitutions, and implementing national policies to ensure the provision of inclusive education (UNICEF, 2021f). For example, Bangladesh ratified CRPD in 2007 and made constitutional changes in 2011 to guarantee free, compulsory education for all children, but has faced implementation challenges such as limited facilities, inaccessible infrastructure, and lack of awareness (Carrington et al., 2019). Sri Lanka's educational reforms began with the Universal Free Education Policy in 1945 and were bolstered by the National Policy on Disability in 2003. However, the country still faces implementation issues related to the continued practice towards special education in segregated settings, which requires the country to conduct a comprehensive review of the legal/policy framework and eliminate provisions that promote segregated forms of education in special school settings (UNICEF, 2021e). Bhutan established the first special school for visually impaired children in 1973 and introduced policies to provide equal educational opportunities for disabled children, yet the commitment to mainstreaming remains insufficient (UNICEF, 2021a). Nepal adopted the Special Education Policy in 1996, ratified the CRPD in 2010, and initiated the Consolidated Equity Strategy in 2014 to create an inclusive system, but implementation is impeded by resource constraints and social and geographical barriers (Regmi, 2017; UNICEF, 2021d).

The above statements echo the fact that countries like Maldives have undergone significant legal and policy reforms over the past decades, reflecting a growing recognition of the importance of inclusive education. Commitment of these countries to IE signifies a shared understanding of the rights of all individuals, thus illuminating a remarkable shift towards fostering inclusive and equitable learning environments, ensuring that every learner has an opportunity to thrive and reach their potential.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a case study approach to investigate the legal process undertaken to establish a nation-wide inclusive education in Maldives.

(a) Data collection methods: We engaged multiple sources of data including legal, policy, and other relevant documents from the local context. Accordingly, a total of 24 formal documents pertaining to four major categories – (1) legislative documents (e.g., laws, regulations, policies, circulars), (2) statistics, and (3) reports produced by relevant agencies, were collected and analysed.

Data analysis methods: Data obtained from the above sources were analysed for their content to attain a comprehensive understanding about the development of a legal framework for IE, and the status of its implementation in the country. Findings derived from all these sources were cross-checked and triangulated to increase the rigour and credibility of the conclusions.

FINDINGS

The Legal Landscape of Inclusive Education in Maldives

Our first research objective seeks to describe the legal sphere of the development and expansion of inclusive education in the country. In doing so, we extended our legal perspectives beyond the acts of law and associated regulations to include available written policy documents, circulars, and the like which we considered as part and parcel of the 'legal' framework. Figure 1 summarises the key developments on the legal domain of inclusive education in the country.

According to Figure 1, the first legal document which is associated with inclusive education that we could locate was the circular from the Ministry of Education (MoE) in 2002. This circular mandated schools nationwide to make special arrangements such as building ramps and establishing facilities such as libraries and laboratories on the ground floor of the school buildings to cater for the needs of students as well as staff and parents who may require special assistance. (Ministry of Education - MoE, 2002). Nonetheless, progression on the legal landscape of inclusive education in the country, except for establishing an inclusive education advisory in 2009, had been rather sluggish until becoming a signatory of the UN convention on the rights of persons with disability (UNCRPD) in 2010. Since then, policies, guidelines, legislations, and laws have gradually emerged shaping the legal atmosphere of IE in the country as depicted in Figure 1.

- 2002 MoE sent a circular to all schools mandating to cater for SEN children and adults
- 2007 Maldives became a signatory of UNCRPD
- 2010 Ratification of UNCRPD
- 2010 Ratification of Disability Act
- 2013 inclusive education policy
- 2015 rolling out the new national curriculum framework
- 2017 introduction of School Improvement, Quality Assurance and Accountability Framework (SIQAAF)
- 2018 department of inclusive education (DoIE) was established
- 2020 ratification of the Education Act
- 2021 revised IE policy in accordance with the Education Act

Figure 1. Key developments of the legal framework of inclusive education in Maldives

Following the signing of UNCRPD, ratification of the same was done in the same year. Moreover, in the same year, the first law ensuring rights of persons with disability known as the law on 'protection of the rights of persons with disabilities and provision of financial assistance' (commonly referred to as the Disability Act) was ratified (Protection of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and Provision of Financial Assistance, Maldives (Law No. 8/2010), 2010). The Disability Act stands as an embodiment of the commitment to ensuring full and effective participation and inclusion of persons with disabilities in society. Further, the Act compels the provision of education without discrimination, promoting the use of suitable facilities and equipment to eradicate barriers to learning. This has facilitated the legal foundation to promote and establish inclusive learning environments for all students.

The inclusive education policy of 2013 was the first detailed legal document that has a significant focus on provision of education to all children in mainstream settings. The policy was aimed to cater for three categories of children, and recommended steps to be taken in providing education to those. These categories are (i) children who need additional learning support, (ii) children with special needs, and (iii) children under special circumstances (Ministry of Education - MoE, 2013). In addition to identification specific groups of children who must be included in the mainstream, who might otherwise be neglected, the policy also stipulates specific responsibilities of all concerned parties towards provision of inclusive education. One of the significant decrees of the policy was about early identification and early intervention of SEN students (as a major responsibility of MoE) stating that schools should be facilitated with resources to identify children with special needs early on, and help to develop their skills at an early stage. Hence, the 2013 inclusive education policy is a crucial document, and perhaps the gold standard, for implementing inclusive education in Maldives.

The implementation of a new national curriculum framework (NCF) in the Maldives in 2015 marked a momentous emphasis on inclusivity, recognising it as an essential component catering to diverse learning needs (National Institute of Education - NIE, 2016). With inclusivity deemed as one of the eight key principles underpinning the curriculum, it clearly delineates the responsibilities of stakeholders in ensuring that the curriculum caters to the needs of all students through adaptive measures (NIE, n.d.).

The School Improvement, Quality Assurance and Accountability Framework (SIQAAF), introduced in 2017 marked the implementation of another inclusive policy related milestones, which signifies a systematic approach to enhancing school quality (MoE, 2017). Under this framework, inclusivity is underscored as one of the five key dimensions of quality school standards.

A significant policy decision in terms of governance of inclusive education is establishment of Department of Inclusive Education (DoIE) in 2018. This has broadened the scope of work whereby the unit is mandated to (i) carry out assessment and intervention, (ii) conduct relevant training and development activities, and establish case management procedures.

The most recent yet the most significant legislative landmark related to inclusive education in the Maldives was the Education Act, ratified by the president in August 2020. According to this Act, the state bears the responsibility to offer equal educational opportunities across all levels of education 2020 (Education Act, Maldives (Law No. 24/2020)). This provision mandates the state to ensure discrimination-free access to education for all children. It further necessitates the state's obligation to establish sufficient resources in schools and train educators and staff, who are competent to understand and address the needs of children with varying abilities including those with disabilities.

Subsequently, significant changes were made to the inclusive education policy in 2021 (MoE, 2021) to align with the new Education Act. One of the most significant changes in the latest revision of the inclusive education policy is to replace the term SEN with the term students with complex learning profile (SCLP) which is a paradigm shift of perspective from segregation to inclusion as well as a shift from discrimination to impartiality.

Implementation

As for the second research objective, we intended to showcase the current state of implementing inclusive education in the Maldives. We acknowledge the efforts of stakeholders to implement inclusive education at the classroom level where emphasis is placed on applying inclusive pedagogy. Moreover, numerous short-term trainings as part of supporting implementing inclusive education policy is also recognised. For example, in the recent years, the Department of Inclusive Education (DoIE) has conducted numerous workshops to build capacity of teachers and relevant staff on catering students with all kinds of special needs, and to create a positive mind-set towards inclusive education (Department of Inclusive Education - DoIE, 2021, 2022). Moreover, to bring a paradigm shift in inclusive education practices in the Maldives, and also to transform practices from segregation to genuine inclusion model, IE pedagogy training and implementation has been conducted in selected schools of Maldives (DoIE, 2022).

While appreciating the above-mentioned efforts, owing to resource limitations bound to the current study, we rely on the assessment of human resources and physical infrastructure for evaluating the implementation of inclusive education in the country.

As for the aspect of human resources, with reference to the Inclusive Education Policy, there should be a minimum of one SEN teacher for every six students who are identified as mild or moderate levels of severity under various categories of students with complex learning profile. This ratio becomes even tighter if the child is diagnosed as a severe or profound case, which requires one teacher for one student. Based on available data, it is estimated that 224 SEN teachers across various levels of schooling are required for schools in the Malé region alone. However, there are only 159 trained SEN teachers and 35 untrained SEN teachers currently employed in these schools (DoIE, 2020). Hence, the most lenient calculations show that there is lack of about 30% trained SEN teachers in the region, let alone other specialised professionals. Further, statistics compiled by DoIE reveal that there is a total of 4248 students with CLP while the total number of available teachers is 368 (DoIE, 2020). Based on the aforementioned method

of calculation, there is a need for at least 708 teachers to cater for the students with CLP whereas the available number of teachers represents only about 52% of the required number. Hence, there is a dire shortage of 48% teachers.

On the aspect of physical infrastructure, unfortunately, there is lack of data to do a national level assessment. However, a recent survey of schools in the capital city conducted by DoIE could shed some light on the condition of these facilities. As reported in the survey, school gates are accessible to SEN students in 87% of schools, while libraries are accessible to only in 56% of schools. Further, school halls and laboratories are accessible to SEN students in as few as 44% of schools. Washrooms are accessible in 69% of schools, while drinking water is accessible in 94%. Moreover, while the playground is accessible to SEN students in 81% of schools, playground equipment is accessible in only 62% of them (DoIE, n.d.). While these findings are limited to only the capital city, there is a high possibility that the condition will be worse if the sample is expanded to the entire nation. Thus, there is a considerable amount of challenges in terms of accessibility to school infrastructure for students with SEN which constitutes to a significant composition of students with CLP.

DISCUSSION AND THE WAY FORWARD

Our findings revealed that Maldives, relative to its geography and economic development, has achieved remarkable milestones on the legal aspect as well as on the move towards inclusive education. Comparing the progression of IE in the South Asian region, we noticed significant variations in the journey of many countries in implementing IE practices. At the same time, significant similarities were also observed. For instance, in Kiribati, an Education Act was enacted in 2013, and several milestones achieved via government initiatives and collaboration done between civil organisations (UNESCO, 2021) by laying local legislations and policies similar to those in the Maldives.

To achieve the full implementation of IE in Maldives, and understand the contributing factors to its success, Kyriazopoulou and Weber (2009)'s *Inputs-Processes-Outcomes* (IPO) model is compared to the findings of this study. The country has adequate legislation and policies in place, as indicated by the *inputs*. The country has established appropriate legislation and policies, as evident in the Education Act and the Inclusive Education Policy, providing a solid legal foundation for inclusivity in education. Additionally, collaboration between the government and civil organisations has led to the development of other local legislations that support implementation of inclusive education. However, in relation to *process* (the second factor of IPO model), there are still some gaps in terms of structural support and capacity building needed for proper implementation of IE. This phenomenon is echoed in several other countries. For instance, Hosshan et al. (2020)'s review of literature highlights similar situations in several Southeast Asian countries, including Malaysia and the Philippines. Parallel to the context of Maldives, delayed policy implementation in these countries might have affected IE nationwide, with teachers lacking sufficient knowledge, resources, and preparation to achieve desired outcomes. In terms of the final factor of IPO, the study does not delve into the *outcomes* of IE, such as academic achievement, social-emotional well-being, and sense of belonging for students with SENs, as these concepts are not within the scope of this study. Hence, those aspects are not discussed here.

Notwithstanding the evolution of the legal landscape, one could question the extent of realising the objectives intended by the laws, regulations, and policies. Our findings on the

Maldives data revealed that efforts of implementing agencies are praiseworthy in terms of pushing inclusive practices particularly in teaching and learning. At the same time, we also argue that crucial structural support and capacity building is still needed to a significant level towards meeting the criteria specified in the respective laws, regulations, and policies. For instance, early identification and intervention of SEN students have not taken place to date, even though it was made mandatory in the first Inclusive Education Policy of 2013. Despite such cases, we limited our discussion to those that were presented in the implementation section above. We also referred to the inclusive education of 2021 (MoE, 2021) and the Education Act (Education Act, Maldives (Law No. 24/2020) in our arguments. Accordingly, we place emphasis on three aspects, namely data, human resources, and physical resources.

Make Data on Inclusive Education Available

As explicated in chapter nine of the education act, one of the mandates to MoE by law is about gathering, storing, and dissemination of educational data (Education Act, Maldives (Law No. 24/2020). In fact, MoE publishes educational statistics every year (eg. MoE, 2021), however these statistics are mostly limited the number students and teachers disaggregated into various demographic factors such as gender and location. Data specific to inclusive education are not yet available in a systematic manner, despite it being a priority in the Maldives education sector plan (ESP) 2019-2013 (MoE & MoHE, 2019). We propagate the necessity to make data gathered on IE are made available to the public or at least to researchers, which is considered a necessary input as identified by the IPO model (Kyriazopoulou & Weber, 2009). Data maintenance and availability are important as they can assist in planning and setting of future goals. Data about SEN students and their educational experiences enable more effective evaluation of programmes, resources, and interventions to facilitate student, school, and national level success. It would also assist in creating legislation that focuses on student achievement, progress, and meeting the set goals of the policy makers. Additionally, the availability of data is crucial for academics and researchers who conduct investigations about the provision of IE in the country.

At present the limited access to data presents multiple challenges for independent researchers to carry out investigations that could have significant policy and practice implications. It is understood that MoE collects volumes of data, whereas the issue is with regard to access to the same. As a way forward, it is postulated that MoE needs to prioritise devising policies with regard to disclosure of data that could be used for scientific investigations. With respect to data on inclusive education, it may be the case that the data could contain sensitive and confidential information of individuals. Hence, a data availability policy should explicate steps that should be taken to ensure anonymity and confidentiality of pupils, while at the same time presenting the same in a format that could be useful for researchers. Such measures would, hopefully, be a step towards realising the obligations mandated by law and specific responsibilities stipulated in the Inclusive Education Policy. Additionally, these would enable independent evaluations of the implementation of IE in a more objective and transparent manner, which are crucial for educational policy and planning.

Scale out Teacher Training for Inclusive Education

Our findings revealed that there is a huge gap in the number of trained professionals for executing IE. Despite the legal provisions for trained teachers which is considered as an input, training teachers as per the policies is also part and parcel of the input deliberated in the IPO model (Kyriazopoulou & Weber, 2009). These include training of SEN teachers to cater for children with all categories of students with CLP. Evidently, there are several students attending schools who require close monitoring and guidance of not only mainstream teachers, but exclusively trained SEN teachers too. With the prevailing deficiency of teachers, achieving the intended outcomes of IE policy is rather impossible. Moreover, given the existing trend in the number of graduates from pre-service teacher training programmes, getting the required number of teacher professionals is far from reach. Hence, concerned authorities need to develop a dedicated nationwide project to scale up training of specialised teachers who are well-prepared not only to work with severe cases of students with CLP, but also conduct early identification and early intervention of SEN students. Such a programme should address specific needs of the schools since more generic policies such as the minimum 'one SEN teacher for each school' policy would not adequately cater the needs, as some schools might have relatively more students with high levels of severity. Ultimately, providing schools with more SEN teachers would increase opportunities to use co-teaching in the required mainstream classes too.

While on one hand, there is the need to scale up teacher training on special education, on the other, there is also a need for providing IE training for general education teachers. In fact, recent efforts by respective authorities resulted in developing teacher training standards for inclusive education that mandates higher education institutions in the Maldives to revise existing modules in teacher training programmes by June 2023. However, the actual implementation of these is yet to happen. What is crucial, in future is to monitor that this has taken shape on the ground to ensure that pre-service teacher training programmes conducted at universities and colleges expedite future teachers' acquisition of inclusive pedagogical knowledge and skills. Further, teacher trainees need to be exposed to model teaching so they can observe and learn techniques from more experienced educators. At the same time, during their peer teaching or practicum, it is crucial for teacher candidates to practice inclusive pedagogies that expose them to first-hand experiences of using the techniques.

Follow Universal Design in Building Codes

The finding reported above highlighted that some essential elements of school infrastructure are not adequately modified to cater for students with CLP as outlined in the relevant legal documents. Some of these modifications, however, are quite easy to incorporate, had those been considered during the planning and construction of school buildings. Hence, as a way forward, we recommend conducting a large-scale assessment on the accessibility to school facilities to all pupils. This assessment should follow a plan of action to address all identified issues in the shortest possible time. This intervention could be equivalent to the process explained in the IPO model (Kyriazopoulou & Weber, 2009). Further, an important government policy priority should be to formulate specific building codes for new schools prepared in line with principles of universal design. These codes, an input in itself as it is a policy directive (Kyriazopoulou & Weber, 2009), should be published and followed in the construction of every new school building in future.

LIMITATIONS

What has been presented in this paper is limited to the understanding obtained from available data sources. There could be many more unpublished policy documents, or undocumented policy initiatives, that were not captured in this study. While such data sources may provide specific details in certain aspects which might broaden the perspectives, the overall picture staged in this work shall remain valid and authentic.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper illustrated the legal landscapes of inclusive education and its implementation in the Maldives. It was discovered that despite the country's geographical and economic peculiarities, Maldives has made praiseworthy legislative strides in its pursuit of a fully functional inclusive education system. The country has endorsed and implemented an adequate legal framework pertaining to both national and international legislations that open avenues for making inclusive education a reality. On the same note, we acknowledge that the country has a considerable distance to go in attaining specific goals set forth by the relevant policies, laws, and other statutory decrees. Following discoveries about the implementation status of these legislations, we recommend a way forward comprising of three specific actions; (i) making data on inclusive education available, (ii) scaling out teacher preparation, and (iii) follow universal design in building codes. We can all agree that improvement of inclusion in school is not only a matter of justice and equal opportunities, but an important element for social growth and cohesion. Hence, to build a better and more inclusive future for all children, stakeholders, policymakers, and educators must prioritise and devote themselves prudently to strengthen inclusive education in the country.

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